

MANAGEMENT FOR IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF LEARNING BASED ON THE FUN SCHOOL MOVEMENT AT PRIMARY SCHOOLS OF TANGERANG DISTRICT (CASE STUDY AT SDN SAGA 06 BALARAJA AND SDN KAMPUNG MELAYU V TELUK NAGA)

YUDI NURSAPYUDIN

Universitas Islam Nusantara, Bandung, West Java, Indonesia. Email: yudinursapyudin@uninus.ac.id

ADE TUTTY R. ROSA

Universitas Islam Nusantara, Bandung, West Java, Indonesia. Email: adetuttyrrosa@uninus.ac.id

AGUS MULYANTO

Universitas Islam Nusantara, Bandung, West Java, Indonesia. Email: agusmulyanto@uninus.ac.id

ANDRIANA GAFFAR

Universitas Islam Nusantara, Bandung, West Java, Indonesia. Email: andrianagaffar@uninus.ac.id

Abstract

Until now, the learning process in primary schools in Kabupaten Tangerang has tended to be teacher-centered. The teacher's job is to deliver the materials and students are given the responsibility to memorize all the knowledge. A change is needed by transforming it into student-centered learning with the fun school movement. This research aims to: 1) Analyze the management program planning for improving the quality of learning based on GSM at SDN Saga 06 Balaraja and SDN Kampung Melayu V Teluk Naga, Tangerang Regency, 2) Examine the problems that arise in the organization of management programs to improve the quality of learning based on GSM at SDN Saga 06 Balaraja and SDN Kampung Melayu V Teluk Naga Tangerang Regency, 3) Examine the problems that arise in the implementation of management programs to improve the quality of learning based on GSM at SDN Saga 06 Balaraja and SDN Kampung Melayu V Teluk Naga Tangerang Regency, and 4) Examine the problems that arise in the supervision of management programs to improve the quality of learning based on GSM at SDN Saga 06 Balaraja and SDN Kampung Melayu V Teluk Naga Tangerang Regency. The research method used in this study is a descriptive method with a qualitative approach. Data collection was done through in-depth interviews, observation and document study. After the data was collected, it was checked for validity and declared valid by triangulation. The results of this study indicate that: 1) Planning is carried out starting from the annual program, semester program, syllabus, lesson plans, all of which become the basis for planning made by teachers, 2) The Principal is assisted by the Vice Principal who organizes the teachers in implementing the learning curriculum, 3) Implementation of learning quality improvement management based on the fun school movement in elementary schools in Tangerang Regency is carried out by socializing to teachers, parents of students so that it can be supported by all parties in order to create more enjoyable learning with four areas of change namely Learning Environment, Pedagogical Practice, Character Development, and School Connectedness, and 4) Supervision at SDN Saga 06 is carried out by education supervisors from the agency, and managerially by the principal assisted by the vice principal.

Keywords: Management, Learning System, Learning Quality, Fun School Movement.

INTRODUCTION

Improving the quality of learning is a whole unity in the learning process, including creativity, independence, cooperation, solidarity, leadership, empathy, tolerance and student life skills in order to form character and improve the civilization and dignity of the nation. To achieve the expected quality, quality learning activities, Permendikbud 81A of 2013 uses the principles that: (1) Student-centered, (2) Develop student creativity, (3) Create fun and challenging conditions, (4) Contain values, ethics, aesthetics, logic, and kinesthetics, and (5) Provide diverse learning experiences through the application of various learning strategies and methods that are fun, contextual, effective, efficient, and meaningful.

Student-centered learning means that in the learning climate in the classroom the teacher is able to optimize all the potential of students, there are various potentials possessed by students in accordance with the nature of creation that each human being has its unique potential just as there is nothing the same between the fingerprints of one student and another student. Student-centered learning means the dominance of the teacher in the learning process as a facilitator, namely facilitating the discovery process in each subject matter, a culture of discovery develops and becomes a culture of thinking, behaving and acting as an inventor, if the teacher is able to facilitate every active student learning activity. Teachers are also able to build students' dreams according to their unique potential. With a student-centered learning climate, students will become more creative, which is able to solve problems faced in different ways. A creative learning ecosystem can only be implemented if the teacher is able to create conditions that are fun and challenging, fun means that in learning activities students do with full awareness and enjoy learning, challenging means that in every lesson the teacher provides stimuli related to material and problems that are relevant to students' daily lives. In addition to building a creative learning ecosystem, teachers are also able to be role models in thinking, namely developing scientific logic, critical thinking. Being a role model in attitude, namely developing ethics and aesthetics so that attitudes and behavior match what is said with what is done. Developing kinesthetics in every learning activity can encourage students to be skilled and productive in every learning activity. The problem with the learning process in primary schools in Kabupaten Tangerang is that the learning process tends to be teacher-centered. The teacher's job is to deliver materials and students are given the responsibility to memorize all knowledge. Target-oriented learning for material mastery has proven successful in short-term memory competitions, but fails to equip children to solve problems in long-term life. In other words, teachers still use conventional methods, which are often done by lecturing. To improve the quality of learning, teachers need to master several ways, so that the planning of strategies, learning methods and the implementation of learning activities always refer to improving the internal ability of students' potential. Increasing internal potential, for example, by applying types of learning strategies that allow students to achieve competence fully, fully and contextually. The most essential, urgent and meaningful problem for further research is how teachers are able to apply a scientifically based learning approach, through observation, using critical questions, conducting experiments, developing reasoning skills and being able to

communicate to meet the demands of change, it requires management from teachers who master various methods and approaches, especially GSM as stated in Permendiknas Number 41 of 2007 and Permendikbud Number 65 of 2013 concerning process standards. This issue is very important to study, especially about the management of improving the quality of GSM-based learning that has been implemented in the 2013 curriculum target elementary schools, namely SDN Saga 06 Balaraja and SDN Kampung Melayu V Teluk Naga in Tangerang Regency. GSM in learning can be paired with a scientific process. The implementation of GSM has not been fully implemented by all teachers because intensive training is needed, and requires teacher preparation which includes mastery of both software and hardware. Software includes application systems, operating systems, financing. Hardware includes tools that support the achievement of an active, creative, effective, challenging, fun learning process, causing initiative, creativity and innovation. From the description of the background of the problem and observations of teachers at SDN Saga 06 Balaraja and SDN Kampung Melayu V Teluk Naga in Kabupaten Tangerang, the following problems can be identified: 1) Teachers have difficulty in understanding the concept of GSM, 2) The 2013 curriculum teacher's book has not specifically described GSM, 3) The 2013 curriculum student book has not systematically described examples of GSM implementation, 4) The role of the Principal is considered insufficient in fostering the implementation of GSM, 5) The role of the School Supervisor has not been maximized in assisting the management of GSM, 6) All teachers have difficulty in managing GSM, 7) Most teachers have not been able to make lesson plans that describe GSM, 8) The implementation of learning has not fully described GSM, 9) In carrying out learning assessment all teachers have difficulty implementing authentic assessment.

RESEARCH METHODS

This research uses a qualitative descriptive method, which means that it is a method by focusing on descriptive characteristics at SDN Saga 06 Balaraja and SDN Kampung Melayu V Teluk Naga Tangerang Regency in implementing GSM intensively and in detail with the aim of developing in-depth knowledge about the object concerned and providing an overview of the implementation of GSM. This research uses a qualitative study that is more in line with the philosophical foundation of research that adheres to the constructivism paradigm. Qualitative studies apply an interpretive and natural approach to research subjects. In addition, the theoretical foundations, namely systems theory, complexity theory and stakeholder theory are more in line with qualitative studies that investigate phenomena holistically, not reducing them to a small number of variables that can be measured. The research sites were selected from schools with learning quality management based on the fun school movement that were expected to provide the best information to answer the research questions. Data were collected through observation, in-depth interviews and documentation studies. As a qualitative study, the researcher acts as the research instrument. The informants selected were people involved in the management of GSM-based learning quality in primary schools in Tangerang district, consisting of school supervisors, principals, vice principals for curriculum, teachers, and

student representatives. Interviews were conducted until they reached data saturation or redundancy where no new information was obtained from further interviews. Interviews were recorded and transcribed into documents. Document studies were conducted by collecting each school's lesson plans, school overviews, end-of-semester assessment reports, and written documents submitted by informants. In addition to primary documents, secondary documents from the internet were also used to confirm and complement primary and secondary data.

RESEARCH RESULT

1. Planning the Fun School Movement at SDN Saga 06 Balaraja

The education quality improvement management system applied in education is a management process to direct and control education units according to quality policies, goals, plans and procedures and their achievement on an ongoing basis. Planning activities become an urgent part of the management process as the first step.

The main purpose of quality improvement planning system activities is to plan to improve quality at every stage of school activities, namely input, process, and output of school management. If there is an error in the input and process of education management, the education actors must immediately make improvements so that the process and results of education can be optimized. The implementation of a quality improvement system allows schools to conduct and improve the quality of the education process and the quality of its graduates strictly. The implementation of a quality improvement system in schools does require a very large and very serious effort, but it has a beneficial impact in the long run, because it can prevent or minimize failures in the education and learning system.

According to the statement of the Head of SDN Saga 06 through interviews regarding planning for improving the quality of learning explained that:

GSM learning-based quality improvement planning activities carried out at SDN Saga 06 are based on the work of the School Development Team which has previously worked to compare the condition of education in schools before the implementation of GSM with the expected conditions after the implementation of GSM. In relation to quality improvement, this school has carried out systematic planning in quality assurance which has made a quality improvement plan in the school work plan. In planning to improve the quality of learning at SDN Saga 06, I involve several components, namely: teachers, students, parents and the school committee. In addition to the components above, facilities and infrastructure are also a necessity in planning for improving the quality of learning in this school. This synergy is important in managing a school whose main activity is learning activities, of course guided by the indicators of the National Education Standards.

The results of the interview above are reinforced by documentation of the minutes of the school meeting with parents about the coordination meeting for the implementation of learning at SDN Saga 06. From the documentation of the minutes of the meeting, it can be seen that the meeting participants totaled 25 people, consisting of 5 school officials and 20 parents.

Furthermore, KS 06 emphasized the focus of the planning prepared in improving the quality of learning, explaining that: The main focus in planning to improve the quality of learning at SDN Saga 06 is directed at two aspects. First, related to academics, directed at the curriculum, admission and coaching of students, improving the qualifications of educators and education personnel by providing opportunities for educators and education personnel to participate in GSM training activities. Improving the implementation of learning is certainly the most urgent thing in practicing quality GSM learning must be supported by these two aspects.

The results of the interview above are corroborated by the principal's work program document in improving quality and in detail explaining the steps of planning, implementation and supervision on curriculum components, students, education and education personnel, facilities and infrastructure, school learning atmosphere, community participation and partnerships, as well as other programs in efforts to improve school quality.

Based on the researcher's observation of the document, it was revealed that in the principal's work program document, curriculum planning begins with forming a curriculum development team that uses rules or regulations as a reference in preparing curriculum programs such as regulations on content standards, graduation standards, process standards and assessment standards.

2. Organizing the Fun School Movement at SDN Saga 06 Balaraja

The results of the interview were confirmed by the document of the principal's work program that had been prepared, which also contained the duties of the vice principal. Likewise, the documentation of the organizational structure of SD Saga 06. Furthermore, the document was observed again to reveal what are the duties of the principal and vice principal of SD Saga 06. In the document, it is written that the principal in carrying out the task of leading the school is assisted by the vice principal.

In the principal's work program document, it is explained that the principal's main tasks are 1) Develop and improve the vision, content and objectives of the school, 2) develop the organizational structure of the school, 3) develop a medium-term work plan and annual work plan, 4) develop school regulations, 5) develop a management information system.

3. Implementation of the Fun School Movement at SDN Saga 06 Balaraja

Since implementing the Fun School Movement, SDN SAGA 06 Balaraja has seen a lot of changes. In addition to a beautiful, beautiful and comfortable environment, the growth of children's character, such as responsibility, discipline, caring, empathy, etc. is more visible. This can be said because after conducting interviews with principals, teachers, students, and student guardians, they agreed to say that the school environment which was designed to be more colorful, greener, no horror spots, more attractive to students and gave a positive impression on students made students feel comfortable and happy with the new school environment, feel at home at school, learning is more fun and exciting, and many activities at school are fun.

4. Monitoring the Implementation of Learning Quality Improvement Based on the Fun School Movement at SDN Saga 06 Balaraja

Related to supervision in this study, researchers conducted several interviews with the most authorized parties to oversee the course of quality learning at SD Saga 06, namely the principal and several vice principals who helped the supervision process to improve the quality of learning. The supervision of improving the quality of learning at SD Saga 06 is carried out in a hierarchical manner, that is, every school must have an education supervisor/supervision assigned by the education office, including SD Saga 06. Likewise, because SD Saga 06 is a public school, supervision is also carried out by the Tangerang District Education Office Branch Office.

5. Planning the Fun School Movement at SDN Kampung Melayu V

The results of the interview above are corroborated by the principal's work program document in improving quality and in detail explaining the steps of planning, implementation and supervision on curriculum components, students, education and education personnel, facilities and infrastructure, school learning atmosphere, community participation and partnerships, as well as other programs in efforts to improve school quality. Based on the researcher's observation of the document, it was revealed that the principal's work program document outlined that curriculum planning begins by forming a curriculum development team that uses rules or regulations as a reference in preparing curriculum programs such as regulations on content standards, graduation standards, process standards and assessment standards. Related to the curriculum is organizing a program that refers to the education calendar and then directs educators to develop a learning program that is socialized to students, parents or school committees. In preparing the curriculum at SDN Kampung Melayu V, the Principal looks at this and is linked to the sociological aspects of the local area, this is done so that the manager knows the needs analysis that exists in all levels of society. Because by looking at the sociological aspects, the manager has inadvertently responded to the wishes of the community as users of the learning quality planning activities at SDN Kampung Melayu V.

6. Organizing the Fun School Movement at SDN Kampung Melayu V

An important part of improving the quality of learning is administratively and financially managed by the treasurer, as expressed by the school treasurer:

There are several technical matters related to improving the quality of learning at SDN Kampung Melayu V, for example, we are the ones who select and appoint educators and education personnel to manage the school, then matters regarding funding for the development of quality improvement programs, administration, SK-SK, and others which can later be elaborated by the principal as the leader of the school through long-term and short-term planning programs.

So the school in an effort to improve the quality of learning plays a role in fostering human resources, financial management and administration and managerial guidance of the principal. The delegation of this task is an organizational form of the Principal to manage

this school along with existing staff such as vice principals and teachers and administrative staff.

7. Implementation of the Fun School Movement at SDN Kampung Melayu V

With the Fun School Movement, it can be a breath of fresh air for the world of education to overcome the problems of conventional learning that is monotonous and tends to be lacking in producing competent graduates. The Fun School Movement invites all education stakeholders to realize that learning in accordance with today's times is learning that is varied, not monotonous, able to keep up with the times, so that it will be fun for students to take part in learning and not feel bored and they can become a qualified generation. Not only intellectually intelligent, but have life skills and good character. The Fun School Movement is a grassroots movement with the aim of changing the paradigm of Indonesian education. The trick is to create a positive school ecosystem so that children's creativity, exploration power and character strength grow optimally. To create a creative, collaborative, empathic, and respectful school ecosystem, changes are made in four areas as a whole, which are the principles of the Fun School Movement.

Based on the results of interviews, observations, and documentation, it can be concluded that in the management of improving the quality of learning based on the fun school movement at SDN Saga 06 and SDN kampong Melayu V, it starts from planning the curriculum field with the formation of a team that makes plans based on government regulations, namely based on the 2013 curriculum. Curriculum planning activities focus on curriculum documents related to syllabus and lesson plans, then the development of school calendars and activity schedules, learning programs that not only contain mandatory learning from the government based on GSM learning.

Planning in the field of educators and education personnel by determining the needs planning team, the task division plan team, the development team, and making rules about giving to educators and education personnel.

Finally, the planning of facilities and infrastructure to support the learning process is an important point that has been planned since the inception of this school. A comfortable place to learn and support character improvement for all school residents is the basic foundation before the learning activities themselves are carried out. Planning in the field of facilities and infrastructure focuses on development and maintenance involving all elements that use school facilities. One of the facilities and infrastructure development plans is to maintain the classrooms so that they are more comfortable for learning.

CONCLUSIONS

The results of the research, analysis and discussion show that the management of improving the quality of learning based on the fun school movement in primary schools in Tangerang district has been implemented in a well-planned manner, but there are still some obstacles and requires a learning system model that has more impact on the quality of student learning. Based on the results of interviews, observations and documentation, it can be concluded that in the management of improving the quality of learning based on

the fun school movement at SDN Saga 06 and SDN kampung Melayu V, it starts from planning the curriculum field with the formation of a team that makes plans based on government regulations, namely based on the 2013 curriculum. Curriculum planning activities focus on curriculum documents related to syllabus and lesson plans, then the development of school calendars and activity schedules, learning programs that not only contain mandatory learning from the government based on GSM learning. The implementation of the Fun School Movement program at SDN Saga 06 Balaraja and SDN Kampung Melayu V Teluk Naga Tangerang Regency obtained information that the four areas of change that became the program of the Fun School Movement in developing student character have been running well. This is evidenced by the running of each activity program and the benefits felt by all school residents, both teachers, students and guardians. Supervision in this study also has an impact on the quality of student learning, therefore external supervision, namely from the Office Branch Office (KCD) is needed to provide input to the Principal in improving the quality of student learning. In addition, the role of the Principal as the leading supervisor in the school can supervise teachers, especially pedagogic supervision so that the teacher's ability to teach will improve. This will ultimately improve the quality of student learning in the classroom.

SUGGESTIONS

Based on the conclusions and implications described above, the following recommendations can be made:

School principal

Should further improve the network with agencies related to the school in order to add insight for students to learn more from the surrounding environment or agencies that are directly related to learning, such as the police, health department or religious leaders.

Improve teachers' pedagogic competence by attending seminars and workshops so that teachers can create fun learning for students in the classroom. Cooperate with parents through the school committee to increase parents' participation in creating a pleasant school environment.

Teachers

Teachers must be able to get out of the comfort zone of teaching habits so far by not changing the learning methods that have been carried out so far by changing learning that is fun for children, for example, doing learning that does not always have to be in the classroom, can be changed in the library, school yard and so on. Improve pedagogic competence by attending seminars and workshops that support their ability to create fun learning for students.

Parents of Students

Increase awareness to the school when the school needs support from parents both morally and materially in creating a fun school movement.

Tangerang District Education Office

Can socialize the fun school movement to all schools so that the fun school movement can be implemented in all schools and can produce students with character.

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